

ELECTROMAGNETIC SHIELDING PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The susceptibility of modern microelectronic systems to electromagnetic interference necessitates an understanding of the electromagnetic properties of composite materials. This paper reports the results of a series of measurements made to determine the electric and magnetic shielding effectiveness of carbon, hybrid and non-carbon fibre composite materials. Samples have been prepared to study the effects of fibre orientation, fibre type, sample lay-up and degree of hybridisation on the electromagnetic shielding properties. Measurements have been made using the dual TEM cell technique. Shielding measurements have been made in the frequency domain over the frequency range of 2 to 200 MHz and in the time domain using a double exponential pulse.

KEYWORDS: Electromagnetic Shielding; Composites; Electric/Magnetic; Carbon/Hybrid/Non-carbon

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of composite materials for the construction of aircraft, such as the F-18 Hornet, advanced helicopters, and minehunter-type ships is becoming increasingly more common because of their superior specific strength and stiffness, ballistic performance, flammability resistance and economic gains. A knowledge of the electromagnetic (EM) properties of these anisotropic laminated materials is necessary because of their limited conductivity and the increased susceptibility of modern electronic systems to electromagnetic pulse (EMP) and electromagnetic interference (EMI) and an electromagnetic environment that is becoming increasingly more severe for both civilian and military operations.

The electromagnetic properties of composite materials have been the subject of a number (1-4) of experimental and analytical studies during the late 1970's and early 1980's. The present study was undertaken as a result of the development of both new experimental techniques as well as new materials which are relevant to various current and future DND systems.

In this paper we report the results of a series of measurements that have been made to determine both the electric and magnetic shielding effectiveness of carbon, non-carbon and hybrid fibre composite materials. The variables examined included the effects of fibre type, conductivity, and orientation, sample lay-up and degree of hybridization. The importance of contact resistance on the effective EM shielding properties was also examined.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials The materials tested were multi-ply unidirectional or cross-ply epoxy matrix composite laminates containing carbon, glass, aramid and boron fibres. The samples were prepared by standard autoclaving procedures and consisted of six or eight-ply laminates. The unidirectional plies were arranged in various orientations (eg. 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$, 90°). Table 1 shows the lay-ups of the samples used in these studies which were 18 cm square. Hybrid laminates were also produced by mixing fibres on a layer to layer basis.

2.2 **Electrical Contact** In order to obtain a proper measurement of the shielding properties of the composite samples, good electrical contact must exist between the sample and the body of the transverse electromagnetic (TEM) cell used to make the measurements. To achieve this, the edges of all of the samples were silver painted and then an aluminum gasket was attached to the painted edge of the sample again using silver paint. Finally, the gasket was painted onto the TEM cell surface. Pressure was applied to the upper cell to ensure good contact between the two cells.

2.3 **Measurement Techniques**

2.3.1 **Dual TEM Cell** To make the EM shielding measurements, a dual TEM cell was used. In this method, two TEM cells are coupled by a common aperture as shown in Figure 1. Measurements are made of the penetration of the EM fields from the driven (lower) cell into the receiving (upper) cell. Insertion loss measurements are made by comparing the results when the aperture is loaded with a composite sample with results for the open (unloaded) aperture.

The theory of the dual TEM cell has been developed by Wilson and Ma (5,6). Provided the aperture dimension is small compared to the wavelength used, small aperture theory can be used and the penetration of the EM fields into the upper cell treated in terms of the equivalent electric and magnetic polarizabilities of the aperture. The output of the cell in the forward direction is related to the sum of the electric and magnetic polarizabilities and in the backwards direction to the difference. Expressions for the forward and backward insertion losses (defined as the ratio of the transmitted power with the material in place to that of an open aperture) are given below.

$$IL_{\text{forward}} = 20 \log \left| \frac{\alpha_{ey} + \alpha_{mx}}{\tilde{\alpha}_{ey} + \tilde{\alpha}_{mx}} \right| \quad \text{and} \quad IL_{\text{backward}} = 20 \log \left| \frac{\alpha_{ey} - \alpha_{mx}}{\tilde{\alpha}_{ey} - \tilde{\alpha}_{mx}} \right|$$

where $\alpha_{ey, mx}$ = open aperture polarizability
 $\tilde{\alpha}_{ey, mx}$ = loaded aperture polarizability

Experimentally (7) it is possible to separate the electric and magnetic properties of the material by adding or subtracting the two outputs of the receiving cell using a hybrid junction which gives;

$$IL_{\Sigma} = 20 \log \left| \frac{\alpha_{cy}}{\alpha_{ey}} \right| \quad \text{and} \quad IL_{\Delta} = 20 \log \left| \frac{\alpha_{mx}}{\alpha_{mx}} \right|$$

The dual TEM cell used in these studies was designed by Dr. S. Kashyap and built at the National Research Council of Canada.

- 2.3.2 Frequency Domain Measurements Measurements of the magnetic and electric insertion loss of the laminates were made over the frequency range from 2 to 200 MHz using a Hewlett Packard HP8753B Network Analyzer. The outputs from the two ends of the receiving TEM cell were combined to give either the sum or difference signals using an Anzac Model HH-107 Hybrid Junction. The range of frequencies measured was limited by the characteristics of the hybrid junction. The TEM cell had the capability of measurements to about 600 MHz before higher order modes were excited.

Values for the insertion loss were obtained by dividing the magnetic and electric shielding effectiveness data for the open aperture by the corresponding results for the aperture loaded with a composite sample. Open aperture results were stored on disk and could be retrieved by the Network Analyzer.

- 2.3.3 Time Domain Measurements A few shielding and insertion loss measurements have also been made in the time domain. In this case, a double exponential pulse was generated using an Analogic Model 2045 Arbitrary Function Generator and fed into the input of the lower TEM cell. The form of the pulse was given by the equation

$$E(t) = 5.0 * (\exp(-\beta t) - \exp(-\alpha t))$$

$$\text{where } \alpha = 4.76 \times 10^8 \text{ s}^{-1} \quad \text{and} \quad \beta = 4.00 \times 10^7 \text{ s}^{-1} \quad (1)$$

The two outputs from the receiving cell were combined in the hybrid junction to give either the sum or difference signal. This signal was then amplified using an EIN Model 411LA broad band amplifier (100 kHz to 300 MHz bandwidth) that provided approximately 40 dB gain. The output was recorded on a Tektronix DSA602 Digitizing Signal Analyzer. The relatively fast falltime was used to minimize distortion of the output signal as a result of the low frequency response of the amplifier.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effect of Fibre Type The effect of fibre type on the magnetic shielding properties of a number of different materials is shown in Figure 2. Interestingly, it is seen that the difference between three types of carbon fibre materials is not large (~5 dB). Various workers, including McMahon (8), have shown that fibre electrical resistivity decreases with increasing elastic modulus. The present carbon fibres have resistivities from approximately $19 \mu\Omega.m$ (AS1 & AS4) to $12 \mu\Omega.m$ (IM6 & IM7). According to the theory of loaded apertures developed by Casey (9,10) and Latham and Lee (11) this difference in fibre conductivity should translate linearly to the shielding characteristics. These higher modulus carbon fibres should therefore be the preferred reinforcement and the present results suggest such a trend. Even higher modulus carbon fibres exist such as P-100 from Union Carbide with a resistivity as low as $5 \mu\Omega.m$. Clearly advantages may exist in mixing carbon fibre types to optimize shielding as well as mechanical properties.

As anticipated, the glass and aramid fibres provide essentially no shielding as they are non-conducting. The boron-epoxy sample on the other hand provides an intermediate degree of shielding as the central core of each fibre is a tungsten filament. This is consistent with conductivity measurements (3) on boron fibres. Thus the choice of boron/epoxy over carbon/epoxy for the repairs of cracks in metallic structures by ARL/RAF in Australia also resulted in limited shielding by the patch material[12].

3.2 Effect of Fibre Orientation Fibre orientation has a major influence on magnetic shielding, as is seen in Figure 3, which shows the magnetic insertion loss of AS-4 carbon composite material having fibres oriented unidirectionally at 0° , 30° , 45° , 60° and 90° to the

direction of propagation of the EM wave. It should be noted that the insertion loss measurements for the 0° sample are probably influenced by the limited dynamic range of the network analyzer.

Qualitatively these results relate directly to the anisotropic conductivity of the composite laminate. The conductivity is greatest along the fibres and, hence, when they are oriented at 0°, there is very little interruption of the current flow along the body of the cell and shielding is high. By comparison, the conductivity transverse to the fibres is lowest leading to poor shielding when the fibres are oriented at 90°.

A simple mathematical model that predicts the shielding properties of unidirectional samples with fibres at arbitrary orientation or samples with multi-directional plies has been developed. In this model, the shielding of a sample oriented at an angle θ is obtained by decomposing the magnetic field into components perpendicular and parallel to the fibres and using the 0° and 90° attenuation data ($ATTN_{\text{parallel}}$ and $ATTN_{\text{perp.}}$) to calculate insertion loss. For a single ply, the transmitted field, H_t , is given by the expression

$$H_t = \sqrt{(H_{\text{parallel}})^2 + (H_{\text{perp.}})^2} \quad (2)$$

where

$$H_{\text{parallel}} = \text{Cos}^2(\theta) \times ATTN_{\text{parallel}} \quad \text{and} \quad H_{\text{perp.}} = \text{Sin}^2(\theta) \times ATTN_{\text{perp.}}$$

For multilayer samples, resistivity is calculated by considering the layers to be connected in parallel electrically. A comparison between experimental values and values calculated using this model for 200 MHz is shown in Figure 4 and Table 2.

Figure 5 indicates that the electric insertion loss is also dependent on fibre orientation. It should be noted that measurement of the electrical shielding properties of the carbon composite samples is limited by the dynamic range of the Network Analyzer especially at the lower frequencies and for the 0° samples. The actual loss is probably higher than measured under these conditions.

Because of the difficulty in making electric shielding measurements on unidirectional 0° and multidirectional samples with high insertion loss, most of the remaining discussion will concentrate on the magnetic properties of the laminates.

3.3 Effect of Lay-Up and Hybridization In Figure 6, the magnetic insertion loss for a number of laminates are compared. This figure shows the effects of degree of hybridization and lay-up. The insertion loss follows the expected trend in sample conductivity. Thus, for example, the insertion loss from 8 layers of carbon fibre (AS-4/0°) is 8-14 dB higher (depending on frequency) than the AS-4/GLASS sample which contains two layers of 0° AS-4 fibre. From simple considerations, one might expect a difference of 12 dB based on sample conductivity.

Since 0° fibres provide high shielding, qualitatively the AS-4/0°, ±60° laminate (which contains two layers of 0° oriented fibre) should provide somewhat higher shielding than the AS-4/GLASS laminate as observed. It is of interest to note that, in a ±45° pair of plies, the plies are orthogonal to each other. This suggests that a ±45° pair should have roughly the same shielding effectiveness as a single 0° oriented ply. On this basis, the insertion loss of the AS-4/±45° and AS-4/0°, ±45°, 90° laminates are expected to lie between the curves for AS-4/GLASS and AS-4/0°. While this is true for low frequencies, the AS-4/±45° curve crosses the AS-4/0° at high frequencies. Two factors may account for this. Firstly the 0° sample is sensitive to slight misorientation and, secondly, for high loss samples the magnetic insertion loss measurements may be affected by the dynamic range of the instrument. It was noticed that the background noise level can vary from day to day.

Estimates of insertion loss based on the model described previously are included in Table 2 for the multidirectional laminates.

3.4 Effect of Contact Resistance on Measurement of Shielding Properties The three curves in Figure 7 show effects of different methods of bonding the AS-4/0° composite sample to the body of the TEM cell on the magnetic insertion loss. The methods of bonding the sample to the TEM cell body were, from top to bottom;

- a) use of a pressure contact.
- b) use of copper tape to bond the laminate to the cell.
- c) use of a metal gasket which was silver painted to both the laminate and cell.

In all cases, the edge of the laminate had been coated with a conducting silver paint to ensure good electrical contact with the end of the carbon fibres.

These results show clearly the importance of making a good electrical contact with the sample if the shielding properties are not to be degraded. From a practical point of view it is clear that attention must be paid to forming low resistance joints when composite panels are joined (for example in aircraft or ship construction) if good shielding is to be maintained. These effects have also been noted previously by Strawe [1].

The theory of the effect of contact resistance on shielding effectiveness has been further discussed by Casey (9). In order to obtain reliable results, the contact resistance must be small compared to the sample resistance.

3.5 Time Domain Measurements Time domain measurements of the magnetic shielding effectiveness of a unidirectional AS-4 sample oriented in the 0° and 90° directions are shown in Figure 8. This Figure shows the output from the upper TEM cell in response to a double exponential pulse. It should also be noted that these measurements are of total shielding effectiveness and include the attenuation effects of the aperture.

As anticipated from the frequency domain measurements, the amplitude of the time domain output pulse is much higher when the laminate is oriented in the 0° direction than in the 90° direction. It should be noted that the shape of the output pulse is different for the two orientations. From a practical point of view, this is important in determining coupling to equipment (for example to cables inside an aircraft or bridge of a ship).

The difference in output pulse shape for the two orientations can be explained in terms of the frequency domain results for the open aperture and laminate insertion loss data. When the sample is oriented at 90° , the shielding effectiveness is dominated by the shielding of the aperture. The attenuation of the open aperture depends [5] inversely on frequency which results in a differentiation of the input pulse. When the laminate is oriented at 0° , the contribution the laminate makes is directly proportional to frequency and the total shielding is essentially frequency independent. Thus while the total signal is attenuated, the output signal shape remains essentially the same as the input pulse.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The dual TEM cell technique has been shown to be a valuable method to measure the magnetic and electric insertion loss of composite materials. The effects of fibre type, fibre orientation, sample lay-up and contact resistance were found to control the EM loss characteristics.

While carbon fibres have resistivities approximately 3 orders of magnitude higher than good metallic conductors (Al, Cu and Ni), they do possess adequate conductivity to provide a substantial shielding to advanced composite structures. However other common reinforcements such as aramid and glass fibres are incapable of providing adequate shielding unless mixed (hybridised) with carbon fibres. The highest modulus fibres are the preferred reinforcement from the standpoint of maximising shielding. Fibre orientation has a major influence on both the magnetic and electric shielding properties of samples having only unidirectional fibres but multidirectional laminates experience less severe orientation effects. The results demonstrated the major importance of obtaining a low resistance contact with the ends of the carbon fibres when composite panels are connected if the intrinsic material shielding properties are to be maintained.

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TABLE 1

PREPARATION OF SAMPLES

<u>MATERIAL</u>	<u># OF PLYS</u>	<u>LAY-UP</u>
AS-4	8	0°
AS-4	8	30°
AS-4	8	45°
AS-4	8	±45°
AS-4	8	0°, ±45°, 90°
AS-4	6	0°, ±60°
AS-4/GLASS	2/AS-4	0°
	6/GLASS	0°
AS-1	8	0°
IM-6	8	0°
IM-7	8	0°
BORON	8	0°

TABLE 2

COMPARISON OF PREDICTED AND CALCULATED INSERTION LOSS (200 MHZ)

<u>SAMPLE LAY-UP</u>	<u>MEASURED I.L.(dB)</u>	<u>CALCULATED I.L.(dB)</u>
AS-4/0°	56.9	-
AS-4/90°	3.0	-
AS-4/30°	15.4	13.2
AS-4/45°	9.0	7.8
AS-4/60°	6.2	4.9
AS-4/±45°	66.0	50.9
AS-4/0°, ±45°, 90°	55.0	48.5
AS-4/GLASS	48.0	44.9
AS-4/0°, ±60°	53.0	39.8

FIGURE 1 - DUAL TEM CELL

FIGURE 2 - EFFECT OF FIBRE TYPE ON MAGNETIC INSERTION LOSS

FIGURE 3 - EFFECT OF FIBRE ORIENTATION ON MAGNETIC INSERTION LOSS

FIGURE 4 - MEASURED AND CALCULATED VALUES OF MAGNETIC INSERTION LOSS (AS-4 LAMINATE WITH UNIDIRECTIONAL FIBRES AT 200 MHz)

FIGURE 5 - EFFECT OF FIBRE ORIENTATION ON ELECTRIC INSERTION LOSS

FIGURE 6 - EFFECT OF LAY-UP ON MAGNETIC INSERTION LOSS

FIGURE 7 - EFFECT OF CONTACT RESISTANCE ON MAGNETIC INSERTION LOSS

FIGURE 8 - TIME DOMAIN SHIELDING EFFECTIVENESS MEASUREMENTS (AS-4 SAMPLE)